

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EFFECT OF SPERMIDINE ON THE EXPRESSION OF EXTRACELLULAR MATRIX PROTEINS AND AUTOPHAGY MARKERS IN HUMAN LUNG FIBROBLASTS

Öncü G.,

Biota Laboratories R&D Center, 34785 Sancaktepe, Istanbul, Türkiye

Türkoğlu M.,

Biota Laboratories R&D Center, 34785 Sancaktepe, Istanbul, Türkiye

Türkan A.,

Biota Laboratories R&D Center, 34785 Sancaktepe, Istanbul, Türkiye

Sevinç H.

Biota Laboratories R&D Center, 34785 Sancaktepe, Istanbul, Türkiye

Abstract

Spermidine is a polyamine involved in cellular homeostasis and longevity and has been reported to regulate both autophagy and inflammation. In this study, the effects of spermidine on the expression of extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins and autophagy markers were investigated in MRC-5 human lung fibroblast cells using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Following spermidine treatment, ECM components, including matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1) and matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9), were increased at 24 h but decreased at 48 h. Hyaluronan synthase-2 (HAS2) expression was increased, whereas elastase levels were decreased at both time points. Spermidine treatment upregulated fibroblast growth factor-2 (FGF-2) but did not affect vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) levels. Moreover, spermidine reduced the expression of the inflammatory cytokines interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), while interleukin-6 (IL-6) levels remained unchanged. Autophagy markers, including Beclin-1 and microtubule-associated protein 1 light chain-3 (LC3), were significantly upregulated. Conversely, spermidine treatment resulted in decreased SIRT1 levels. Overall, these findings suggest that spermidine enhances ECM remodeling and autophagy while attenuating inflammatory responses. These results highlight the potential significance of spermidine supplementation in lung extracellular matrix remodeling.

Keywords: Spermidine; MRC-5 cells; Extracellular matrix remodeling; Autophagy markers; ELISA.

1. Introduction

Spermidine (SPD) is a natural polyamine found in mammalian cells and is essential for a wide range of cellular processes (Madeo, 2018). It is synthesized endogenously but can also be obtained from dietary sources such as cheese, mushrooms, grains, and legumes (Atiya, 2011; Kim, 2021). Biochemically, spermidine plays a critical role in cellular functions including DNA and RNA stabilization, regulation of gene expression, and control of cell proliferation (Minois, 2014). One of its most important functions is the induction of autophagy, thereby maintaining proteostasis and cellular integrity. Impaired autophagy is considered a hallmark of aging and leads to loss of proteostasis, accumulation of damaged organelles, and increased susceptibility to age-associated diseases (Levine & Kroemer, 2008; Rubinsztein, 2011; Schmauck-Medina et al., 2022).

Notably, intracellular spermidine levels decline significantly with age, paralleling the reduction in autophagic activity (Scalabrino, 1984). Previous studies have demonstrated that spermidine supplementation extends lifespan in various model organisms, including yeast, flies, nematodes, and human immune cells, primarily through the induction of autophagy and a reduction in oxidative stress (Eisenberg et al., 2009). More recent research has shown that spermidine supplementation can reverse age-related cardiac deterioration, preserve cognitive function, and reduce systemic inflammation (Ni et al., 2021; Pekar et al., 2020; Madeo

et al., 2019; Hofer et al., 2022). Furthermore, epidemiological studies indicate that higher dietary intake of spermidine is associated with reduced all-cause mortality and a lower incidence of cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases (Eisenberg et al., 2016; Kiechl et al., 2018). Collectively, these findings underscore spermidine's potential as a therapeutic agent for promoting healthy aging and extending lifespan.

In this context, the present study investigates the ability of spermidine to modulate key cellular processes in MRC-5 human lung fibroblast cells. MRC-5 cells represent a robust and physiologically relevant *in vitro* model for pulmonary research and are widely used in studies focusing on fibrosis, wound healing, and extracellular matrix (ECM) remodeling (Pan et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2025). Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the effects of spermidine on lung health by examining its influence on ECM composition, pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, growth factor levels, and autophagy-related markers.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Cell Culture

The human lung fibroblast cell line MRC-5 was purchased from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, USA). Cells were cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM; Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS; Sigma-Aldrich, USA), 2 mM L-glutamine (Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (Sigma-Aldrich, USA).

Cells were maintained at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. The culture medium was replaced every 2–3 days, and cells were passaged at 80–90% confluency.

2.1 Cell Viability Assay

Cell viability and determination of non-toxic spermidine concentrations were assessed using the 2,3-bis(2-methoxy-4-nitro-5-sulphophenyl)-2H-tetrazolium-5-carboxanilide (XTT) assay (Roche Diagnostics, Germany) following the manufacturer's instructions. MRC-5 cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 1×10^4 cells/well and incubated overnight for attachment. Cells were then treated with spermidine ($\geq 98\%$ purity; Xi'an Natural Field Bio-Technique, China) at concentrations ranging from 10 to 100 μM for 24 and 48 hours. After treatment, 50 μL of the XTT labeling mixture was added to each well and incubated for 4 hours at 37°C. Absorbance was measured at 490 nm with a reference wavelength of 650 nm using a microplate reader (Bio-Rad, USA). Cell viability was expressed as a percentage relative to the untreated control group.

2.2 Spermidine Treatment for Protein Analysis

MRC-5 cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^5 cells/well into 6-well microplates and incubated overnight to allow cell attachment. To determine the protein levels of Interleukin-6 (IL-6), Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β), and Tumor necrosis factor- alpha (TNF- α), the cells were treated with 15, 25, and 50 μM spermidine for 24 hours. For the measurement of Matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1), Matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9), elastase, Hyaluronan synthase 2 (HAS2), Fibroblast growth factor-2 (FGF-2), and Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), the cells were treated with 15 μM SPD for 24 and 48 hours. After the incubation period, cell culture supernatants were collected and centrifuged to remove cell debris. The clarified supernatants were aliquoted and stored at -80°C until further analysis. For the analysis of Beclin-1, MAPLC3, and SIRT1 proteins related to autophagy, MRC-5 cells were seeded at a density of 1×10^6 cells/flask in T25 culture flasks and incubated overnight for adherence. The cells were then treated with 15 and 50 μM SPD for 24 hours.

At the end of the incubation period, the cells were collected and washed twice with cold Dulbecco's phosphate-buffered saline (dPBS, Pan Biotech, Germany). Protease inhibitor cocktail (Thermo Scientific, USA) was added to cold PBS, and cells were lysed by five freeze–thaw cycles. Briefly, cell suspensions were frozen at -80°C and then thawed at room temperature. This process was repeated five times to ensure complete cell disruption. The lysates were centrifuged at $6000 \times g$ for 10 minutes at 4°C . The supernatants were aliquoted and stored at -80°C until further use for protein quantification using the Bicinchoninic Acid (BCA) assay and for subsequent enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) analyses.

2.3 ELISA Analysis

The protein concentrations in the cell lysates were measured using a BCA assay kit (Thermo Scientific, USA) for normalization across samples. Levels of IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , MMP-1, MMP-9, HAS2, elastase, VEGF, FGF-2, Beclin-1, SIRT1 and MAPLC3 were measured using ELISA kits (YL Biont, China) according to the manufacturer's protocols. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm using a microplate reader (Bio-Rad, USA). All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.4 Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate, and data are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical differences were evaluated using Student's *t*-test or one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post-hoc test. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant. Data analysis was performed using OriginLab software (version 10.25).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Effect of spermidine on the cell viability of MRC-5 cells

To determine the non-cytotoxic concentrations of spermidine, MRC-5 cells were treated with various doses of the compound for 24 and 48 hours. The XTT assay indicated that concentrations up to 50 μM were non-cytotoxic at both time points; however, at 100 μM , cell viability was markedly reduced (Fig.1). Therefore, subsequent experiments were conducted below 100 μM .

Figure 1. Effect of spermidine on the cell viability of MRC-5 cells. The cells were treated with indicated concentrations of spermidine for 24 h and 48 h. Values represent the means \pm SD of three independent experiments.

3.2. Effect of spermidine on expression of growth factors in MRC-5 cells

Lung tissue produces VEGF and FGF-2 which are important growth factors necessary for building the lung tissue architecture. To evaluate whether spermidine influences growth factor signaling in MRC-5 cells, we examined its effect on the expression of FGF-2 and

VEGF. Spermidine at 15 μ M significantly upregulated the expression of FGF-2 at both 24 and 48 hours (Fig. 2A), whereas the expression of VEGF was not significantly affected by spermidine (Fig. 2B). These findings suggest that spermidine may promote cell proliferation through the induction of FGF-2.

Figure 2. Effect of spermidine on the expression of growth factors FGF-2 (A) and VEGF (B) in MRC-5 cells. Values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$ independent experiments). Statistical comparisons were performed between groups, with significance indicated above the bars (ns, not significant).

3.3. Effect of Spermidine on the Inflammatory Response of MRC-5 cells

To determine the effect of spermidine on the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines in MRC-5 fibroblast cells, the protein levels of interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumor necrosis factor- α

(TNF- α) were measured in the culture supernatant. As shown in Fig. 3A and 3B, IL-1 β and TNF- α protein levels significantly decreased with increasing concentrations of spermidine, whereas no significant effect was observed on IL-6 expression (Fig. 3C).

Figure 3. Effect of spermidine on the expression levels of IL-1 β (A), TNF- α (B) and IL-6 (C). Values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$ independent experiments). Statistical comparisons were performed between groups, with significance indicated above the bars (ns, not significant).

3.4. Effect of Spermidine on the expression of MMP-1, MMP-9, HAS2 and Elastase

Matrix metalloproteinases MMP-1 and MMP-9 play crucial roles in fibroblast-mediated extracellular matrix (ECM) remodeling, which is essential for tissue repair, wound healing, and the regulation of inflammation. We first investigated the effect of spermidine on MMP-1 and MMP-9 protein levels. As shown in Fig. 4A and 4B, the levels of MMP-1 and MMP-9 significantly increased in the presence of 15 μ M spermidine at 24 h but markedly decreased at 48 h.

Furthermore, hyaluronic acid (HA) and elastin are two major components of the ECM. Therefore, we also examined the impact of spermidine on HAS2, a key enzyme responsible for synthesizing HA, and on elastase, a protease that degrades elastin. Figure 4C shows that the protein levels of HAS2 increased at both 24 h and 48 h following spermidine treatment, whereas elastase levels decreased at both time points, with a more pronounced reduction observed at 48 h (Fig. 4D).

Figure 4. Effect of spermidine on the expression levels of MMP-1 (A), MMP-9 (B), HAS2 (C) and Elastase (D). Values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$ independent experiments). Statistical comparisons were performed between groups, with significance indicated above the bars (ns, not significant).

3.5. Effect of Spermidine on the expression of Sirtuin1 and autophagy markers, Beclin1 and MAP-LC3.

To assess whether spermidine induces autophagy in MRC-5 cells, the protein levels of autophagy markers Beclin-1 and MAP-LC3, and SIRT1 were measured

in cell lysates in the presence and absence of spermidine. The protein levels of Beclin-1 and MAP-LC3 significantly increased following spermidine treatment (Fig. 5A and 5B). On the other hand, SIRT1 levels decreased (Fig. 5C).

Figure 5. Effect of spermidine on the expression levels of BECLIN-1 (A), MAPLC-3 (B), and SIRT-1 (C). Values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$ independent experiments). Statistical comparisons were performed between groups, with significance indicated above the bars (ns, not significant).

4. DISCUSSION

Initially, we investigated the effects of spermidine on the expression of extracellular matrix (ECM)–regulating enzymes, specifically matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1), matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9), hyaluronan synthase-2 (HAS-2), and elastase. Our results demonstrated that spermidine exerted a biphasic effect on MMP-1 and MMP-9 expression, characterized by upregulation at 24 hours followed by downregulation at 48 hours. This transient increase in MMP-1 and MMP-9 may reflect an early remodeling response that supports cellular adaptation or proliferation, whereas their subsequent downregulation at 48 hours may serve to preserve ECM integrity. Matrix metalloproteinases are key regulators of ECM turnover and have been extensively implicated in lung fibrosis and tissue remodeling (Chen et al., 2023; Bormann et al., 2022).

In addition, spermidine treatment increased HAS-2 expression while decreasing elastase levels at both 24 and 48 hours, suggesting enhanced ECM synthesis concomitant with reduced ECM degradation. These findings are consistent with studies in oral tissue regeneration models, where spermidine and hyaluronic acid–based formulations promoted matrix deposition and tissue repair (Henin et al., 2025).

Our study further demonstrated that spermidine significantly upregulated fibroblast growth factor-2 (FGF-2) expression at both 24 and 48 hours, whereas vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) levels remained unchanged. Spermidine has previously been shown to enhance proliferation in a variety of cell

types, including intestinal epithelial cells and dermal fibroblasts (Sugiura et al., 1984; Wei et al., 2022; Flory et al., 2023). The lack of change in VEGF expression suggests that spermidine-induced proliferative responses may occur independently of angiogenic signaling. This observation is supported by evidence indicating that FGF-2 plays a central role in ECM remodeling through regulation of MMP activity and attenuation of fibrotic responses (Svystonyuk et al., 2015; Liguori et al., 2018).

Spermidine treatment also resulted in a significant reduction in the pro-inflammatory cytokines interleukin-1 β (IL-1 β) and tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), despite the absence of prior inflammatory stimulation in MRC-5 cells. In contrast, interleukin-6 (IL-6) levels remained largely unchanged. These findings suggest that spermidine does not cause a broad suppression of cytokine production but rather selectively modulates specific inflammatory pathways. This is consistent with previous reports describing spermidine’s anti-inflammatory properties, which are mediated through suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines and regulation of macrophage activation (Choi et al., 2012; Yang et al., 2016; Li et al., 2022). Mechanistically, spermidine has been shown to inhibit NF- κ B signaling and NLRP3 inflammasome activation, thereby reducing cytokine secretion and inflammatory responses (Guo et al., 2024; Qi et al., 2024).

Finally, spermidine significantly increased the levels of autophagy markers Beclin-1 and microtubule-associated protein 1 light chain-3 (MAP-LC3), supporting its role as a potent autophagy inducer. This effect has been widely reported across multiple cell

types and species (Eisenberg et al., 2009; D'Adamo et al., 2020). Notably, spermidine treatment was also associated with reduced SIRT1 protein levels in our study. While spermidine-induced autophagy has previously been shown to occur independently of SIRT1 in human cells, yeast, and nematodes (Morselli et al., 2011), the observed decrease in SIRT1 expression represents a novel finding and warrants further mechanistic investigation.

CONCLUSION

Spermidine promotes ECM remodeling, enhances fibroblast proliferation, suppresses pro-inflammatory cytokine production, and induces autophagy-related markers in MRC-5 cells. Collectively, these results suggest that spermidine supplementation and spermidine-rich diets may represent promising approaches for supporting pulmonary health.

DECLARATION

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT (OpenAI)/Grok (xAI) in order to assist with grammar and language refinement. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

References

- Atiya, A., Poortvliet, E., Strömberg, R., & Yngve, A. (2011). Polyamines in foods: Development of a food database. *Food & Nutrition Research*, 55(1), 5572. <https://doi.org/10.3402/fnr.v55i0.5572>
- Bormann, T., Maus, R., Stolper, J., Tort Tarrés, M., Brandenberger, C., Wedekind, D., ... & Maus, U. A. (2022). Role of matrix metalloproteinase-2 and MMP-9 in experimental lung fibrosis in mice. *Respiratory research*, 23(1), 180.
- Chen, K., Xu, M., Lu, F., & He, Y. (2023). Development of matrix metalloproteinases-mediated extracellular matrix remodeling in regenerative medicine: A mini review. *Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine*, 20, 661–670. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13770-023-00536-x>
- Choi, Y. H., & Park, H. Y. (2012). Anti-inflammatory effects of spermidine in lipopolysaccharide-stimulated BV2 microglial cells. *Journal of Biomedical Science*, 19(1), 31. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1423-0127-19-31>
- D'Adamo, S., Cetrullo, S., Guidotti, S., Silvestri, Y., Minguzzi, M., Santi, S., ... & Borzì, R. M. (2020). Spermidine rescues the deregulated autophagic response to oxidative stress of osteoarthritic chondrocytes. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine*, 153, 159–172.
- Eisenberg, T., Knauer, H., Schauer, A., Büttner, S., Ruckstuhl, C., Carmona-Gutierrez, D., ... & Madeo, F. (2009). Induction of autophagy by spermidine promotes longevity. *Nature Cell Biology*, 11(11), 1305–1314. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncb1975>
- Eisenberg, T., Abdellatif, M., Schroeder, S., Primessnig, U., Stekovic, S., Pendl, T., ... & Madeo, F. (2016). Cardioprotection and lifespan extension by the natural polyamine spermidine. *Nature Medicine*, 22(12), 1428–1438. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nm.4222>
- Flory, M., Gao, A., Morrow, M., & Alam, A. (2023). Colonic spermidine promotes proliferation and migration of intestinal epithelial cells. *bioRxiv*, 2023-09.
- Guo, X., Feng, X., Yang, Y., Zhang, H., & Bai, L. (2024). Spermidine attenuates chondrocyte inflammation and cellular pyroptosis through the AhR/NF- κ B axis and the NLRP3/caspase-1/GSDMD pathway. *Frontiers in Immunology*, 15, 1462777. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fimmu.2024.1462777>
- Henin, D., Canciani, E., Carmagnola, D., Ferrero, S., Pellegrini, G., Perrotta, M., ... & Gagliano, N. (2025). Morphological and Molecular Evaluation of a Gel Based on Hyaluronic Acid and Spermidine for Oral Regenerative Purposes. *Cells*, 14(14), 1047.
- Hofer, S. J., Davinelli, S., Bergmann, M., Scognamiglio, A., & Madeo, F. (2022). Spermidine supplementation in older adults: A double-blind randomized controlled trial. *Nature Aging*, 2(8), 800–812. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43587-022-00238-2>
- Kiechl, S., Pechlaner, R., Willeit, P., Notdurfter, M., Paulweber, B., Willeit, K., ... & Willeit, J. (2018). Higher spermidine intake is linked to lower mortality: A prospective population-based study. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 108(2), 371–380. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajcn/nqy102>
- Kim, G., Kim, M., Kim, M., Park, C., Yoon, Y., Lim, D. H., ... & Lee, D. G. (2021). Spermidine-induced recovery of human dermal structure and barrier function by skin microbiome. *Communications Biology*, 4(1), 231. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-021-01758-8>
- Levine, B., & Kroemer, G. (2008). Autophagy in the pathogenesis of disease. *Cell*, 132(1), 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2007.12.018>
- Li, X., Zhou, X., Liu, X., Li, X., Jiang, X., Shi, B., & Wang, S. (2022). Spermidine protects against acute kidney injury by modulating macrophage NLRP3 inflammasome activation and mitochondrial respiration in an eIF5A hypusination-related pathway. *Molecular Medicine*, 28(103). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s10020-022-00533-1>
- Liguori, T. T. A., Romero, G., Moreira, L. F. P., & Harmsen, M. C. (2018). Fibroblast growth factor-2 inhibits TGF- β 1-induced differentiation of human cardiac fibroblasts into myofibroblasts. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1), 147. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-34747-3>
- Madeo, F., Eisenberg, T., Pietrocola, F., & Kroemer, G. (2018). Spermidine in health and disease. *Science*, 359(6374), eaan2788. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aan2788>
- Madeo, F., Bauer, M. A., Carmona-Gutierrez, D., & Kroemer, G. (2019). Spermidine: a physiological autophagy inducer acting as an anti-aging vitamin in humans?. *Autophagy*, 15(1), 165–168.
- Minois, N. (2014). Molecular basis of the 'anti-aging' effect of spermidine and other natural polyamines—a mini-review. *Gerontology*, 60(4), 319–326. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000356748>
- Morselli, E., Mariño, G., Bennetzen, M. V., Eisenberg, T., Megalou, E., Schroeder, S., ... & Kroemer, G. (2011). Spermidine and resveratrol induce autophagy by distinct pathways converging on the acetylproteome. *Journal of Cell Biology*, 192(4), 615–629.

21. Ni, Y.-Q., & Liu, Y.-S. (2021). New insights into the roles and mechanisms of spermidine in aging and age-related diseases. *Aging and Disease*, 12(8), 1948–1963. <https://doi.org/10.14336/AD.2021.0603>
22. Pan, R., Zhang, Y., Zheng, M., Zang, B., & Jin, M. (2017). Hydroxysafflor Yellow A suppresses MRC-5 cell activation induced by TGF- β 1 by blocking TGF- β 1 binding to T β RII. *Frontiers in Pharmacology*, 8, 264. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2017.00264>
23. Pekar, T., et al. (2020). Spermidine and cognitive aging: Evidence from human studies. *Journal of Gerontology: Biological Sciences*, 75(7), 1234–1242. <https://doi.org/10.1093/gerona/glz293>
24. Qi, R., Liang, R., Cai, Q., Niu, L., Huang, X., Zhang, D., ... & Yu, P. (2024). The role of NLRP3 inflammasome in aging and age-related diseases. *Immunity & Ageing*, 21(14). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12979-023-00395-z>
25. Rubinsztein, D. C., et al. (2011). Autophagy and aging. *Cell*, 146(5), 682–695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2011.07.030>
26. Scalabrino, G., & Ferioli, M. E. (1984). Polyamines in mammalian aging: An oncological problem, too? A review. *Mechanisms of Ageing and Development*, 26(2–3), 149–164. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-6374\(84\)90004-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0047-6374(84)90004-1)
27. Schmauck-Medina, T., Molière, A., Lautrup, S., Zhang, J., Chlopicki, S., Madsen, H. B., ... & Fang, E. F. (2022). New hallmarks of ageing: a 2022 Copenhagen ageing meeting summary. *Aging (Albany NY)*, 14(16), 6829.
28. Sugiura, M., Shafman, T., Mitchell, T., Griffin, J., & Kufe, D. (1984). Involvement of spermidine in proliferation and differentiation of human promyelocytic leukemia cells.
29. Svystonyuk, D. A., Ngu, J. M., Mewhort, H. E., Lipon, B. D., Teng, G., Guzzardi, D. G., ... & Fedak, P. W. (2015). Fibroblast growth factor-2 regulates human cardiac myofibroblast-mediated extracellular matrix remodeling. *Journal of translational medicine*, 13(1), 147.
30. Wei, Z., Cai, L., Zhao, X., Jiang, X. R., & Li, X. L. (2022). Effects of spermidine on cell proliferation, migration, and inflammatory response in porcine enterocytes. *Frontiers in Bioscience-Landmark*, 27(6), 165. <https://doi.org/10.31083/j.fbl2706165>
31. Wu, Z., Zhu, X., Mao, S., Yang, Y., Liu, X., Liu, Q., Zhang, N., Yang, Y., Li, Y., Gao, M., Bao, J., Li, W., & Li, Y. (2025). Biomimetic topological micro-pattern arrays regulate the heterogeneity of cellular fates in lung fibroblasts between fibrosis and invasion. *ACS Nano*. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.4c11113>
32. Yang, Q., Zheng, C., Cao, J., Cao, G., Shou, P., Lin, L., ... & Shi, Y. (2016). Spermidine alleviates experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis through inducing inhibitory macrophages. *Cell Death & Differentiation*, 23(12), 1850–1861. <https://doi.org/10.1038/cdd.2016.71>